

Research

Factors of prolong stay in hospital after surgery of laparoscopic cholecystectomy

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Abstract: Objective: The aim of this study is to identify different factors which are accountable for prolong stay after surgery after the LC (Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy).

Methodology: This was an observational research work conducted in a period of five years from April 2016 to March 2021 in affiliated Hospital of Southwest Medical University, Luzhou China. There were total five hundred and eighty patients suffering from symptomatic cholelithiasis, who got admission in the hospital and underwent LC. We observed all the patients on the 1st day after surgery to the discharge day from the hospital and we recorded the various intra-operative, postoperative & variables related to patients which were accountable for the prolong stay of the patients in the hospital on a well-organized Performa. Forty-eight hours was the duration decided for short hospital stay and duration of more than two days was the prolong stay.

Results: Out of total five hundred and eighty patients, 32.24% (n: 87) patients were available with prolonged stay in the hospital from three to twenty-eight days. Most of the patients (58.790%) in their 4th and 5th decade of life was suffering from pain in their right hypochondria & pain in right hypochondria in addition with the pain in epigastrium (27.60%) were available as the major clinical aspects. We identified total 28 variables comprising ten patients associated (15.860%), 12 related to surgery (16.55%) & six related to after surgery (16.380%) which gave their full contribution in the prolong stay of the patients in the hospital. Patients available with co-morbid conditions, complicate procedure of operation and main complication after surgery were the important factors for the prolong stay in the hospital.

Conclusion: The reduction in the prolong stay in the hospital is possible with the extreme care during assessment of the patients before surgery. Proper management after the surgery and meticulous surgery are other important factors which can reduce the prolonged hospital stay of the patients.

Keywords: LC, Prolong, Occurrence, Hypochondria, Meticulous, Epigastrium, Co-Morbid.

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Introduction

postoperative stay of the patients in the hospital is very effective feature to evaluate the results of surgical intervention. Short duration stay decreases the cost, reduced the mental trauma and it also determines to early return to the normal

life after recovery. While prolonged stay increases mental trauma, morbidity and it is also much expensive [1]. There is need of minimal invasive surgery to reducing the stay in the hospital with less morbidity as well as mortality [2]. LC is recently very frequent minimally invasive method performed in the whole world as a standard. Its application is possible as a day case surgery or as an ambulatory method [3, 4] or as an outpatient LC [5, 6]. One of the main reasons of admissions in the hospital and high morbidity rate is gall stones [7]. These complications have impact on 10% to 15% adult people of United States of America and 17.0% in United Kingdom with overall prevalence of 3% to 20% [8, 9]. The rate of occurrence of the gall stones in our country Pakistan is 15.0% and it is accountable for 22.0% admissions of the patients in the surgical department of hospitals [10, 11].

Open cholecystectomy was the main traditional method for the treatment of this disease since last one hundred years but now laparoscopic method is available after 1990, which has reduced the stay in the hospital from seven days to only one or two days [12, 13]. There is an estimation that 75% to 95% of all cholecystectomies in various centers of health care are in use as minimal invasive procedure [14, 15].

Methodology

This was an observational research work conducted on five hundred and eighty patients suffering from cholelithiasis from April 2016 to March 2021 in the surgical units of affiliated Hospital of Southwest Medical University, Luzhou China. We explained the whole procedure to the patients and we included all the patients after obtaining their written consent. We completed normal evaluations and examinations in each patient. We gave the main stress of various variables associated with the prolonged stay in the hospital. The division of these variables carried out into factors associated with patients, factors of intra surgery and after surgery. We recorded all the parameters on a well-organized Performa. SPSS V.17 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information. Patients suffering from other malignancies of serious nature were not the part of this research work. Forty-eight hours was the duration of short hospital stay and more than two days as the duration of prolonged stay in hospital. The determination of the relationship between different factors linked with prolonged stay in the hospital carried out with the utilization of the Chi square test. P value of less than 0.050 was significant.

Results

We evaluated five hundred and eighty patients suffering from cholelithiasis in the complete duration of five years for various factors accountable for prolonged stay in the hospital after surgery. In this current research work average stay of the patients in the hospital was 3.750 days. The median age of the patients in this research was 43.50 years and female patients outnumbered the male patients. Various factors associated with patients are available in in Table-1.

Table-1: Variables Associated With Patients

Factors associated with patients	Total	Prolonged stay	Percentage of prolonged stay	P-value
ASA III & IV Score	47	15	2.580%	0.96
Gender (Males)	105	23	3.960%	0.012
Old age (above 60 years)	66	13	2.240%	0.021
Obesity	20	7	1.210%	0.788
Diabetes mellitus	23	5	0.860%	0.271
Hypertension	32	9	1.550%	0.608

Ischemic heart disease	9	3	0.520%	0.944
COPD	13	3	0.520%	0.475
Diabetes mellitus & hypertension	11	4	0.690%	0.768
Past abdominal surgery	35	10	1.720%	0.632

Chart-1 is elaborating the amount of the patients with prolonged stay in the hospital with patient related variables.

The average time of surgery was 47.750 minutes. The factors associated with surgery comprising of the status of surgeons and different other problems of surgery experienced during operation are available in Table-2.

VARIABLES	Total	Prolonged stay	Percentage of prolonged stay	P-value
Operation by Senior consultants	310	7	1.200%	<0.001*
Operation by junior consultants	270	25	4.300%	<0.001*
Dense adhesions around G. B	23	8	1.380%	0.79
Gallbladder with thick wall	29	5	0.860%	0.076
Acute cholecystitis	16	6	1.030%	0.648
Empyema of gallbladder	26	9	1.550%	0.791
Perforation of G. Bladder	10	3	0.520%	0.878
Spillage of stones.	7	2	0.340%	0.834
Bleeding	35	16	2.760%	0.079
CBD Injury	9	5	0.860%	0.132
Cystic Duct avulsion	12	4	0.690%	0.935
Duration of procedure	75	13	2.240%	0.003*

Chart-2 is describing the variables linked with surgery with total amount and prolonged stay patients.

The factors associated with after surgery included factors of recovery after surgery and minor & major complication after surgery as presented in Table-3.

AFTER SURGERY FACTORS	Total	Prolonged stay	%	P-value
Post-Operative Pain.	75	17	2.930%	0.057
Nausea & vomiting	87	15	2.590%	0.001*
Lethargy	95	13	2.240%	<0.001*
Operation Phobia.	65	15	2.590%	0.093
Minor complication.	85	10	1.720%	<0.001*
Major complications.	25	25	4.310%	<0.001*

Chart-3 is elaborating the variables associated with post-operation, total amount of patients with the proportion of the patients with the prolong hospital stay are available in from of different variables. The analysis of all combined twenty-eight variables from every category of the patients, 32.240% (n: 187) patients were available with prolonged stay in the hospital because of one or more factors.

DISCUSSION

There are many advantages of LC over traditional procedures as less stay in the hospital, early recovery, less expense and low rate of morbidity. There is too much attraction of these benefits to the health care professionals [16]. This research work has emphasized some number of factors which are accountable for prolonged stay of the patients in hospital and they will support the professions to obtain the aims of the procedure. The variables related with patients are age, sex, classification of risk of ASA, co-morbidity & past surgical intervention of abdomen. Patients with elder age are always present with complicated nature of disease [2]. In current research work, 2.24% patients greater than sixty years of age were available with prolonged hospital stay. We also concluded an enhanced stay in hospital in the male gender with 3.96% in current work. This is very much like the results of Al-Mulhim AA [17]. In this research study, 2.58% patients with ASA score-3 & 4 had prolonged hospital stay which is highly comparable with the outcomes of Issa ME [18]. There was high conversion rate in the patients having previous history of surgery of abdomen and they had prolonged hospital stay [19]. In current research work, 2.24% patients operated for greater than two hours, 1.38% patients were available with dense adhesions, 0.86% patients had gallbladder with thick wall some other complications these results are very much similar with the findings of Lyass S & Tsang YY [20, 21].

The proportion and extremity of the complications can affect the duration of the stay in hospital as well as recovery time [22]. Pain after surgery (20.0%) and vomiting & nausea (70.0%) are very common distressing aspects for prolonged stay in the hospital after the application of the LC. In current research work, seventeen (2.93%) patients & fifteen (2.59%) patients were available with pain and vomiting & nausea after surgery respectively had prolonged hospital stay, though Tsang YY [21] discovered twenty-nine patients with pain in wound and nineteen patients with nausea & vomiting after surgery [21]. Early mobilization can improve the recovery after application of LC [23, 24]. Major complications after the surgery are the most important reasons to prolong the stay of the patients in hospital [2]. In this current research work, 4.310% patients appeared with major complications and 1.720% patients appeared with minor complications.

Approximately 67.760% patients were available with small stay (from 1 to 2 days) while 32.240% patients were available with prolonged hospital stay (from 3 to 28 days) with an average stay of 3.750 days. In the research work of Tsang YY [21], 44.20% patients got discharge within one days having the minimum stay and 55.80 patients after one day having prolonged stay which is much higher than this research work. The average stays in the hospital as concluded by Rooh-ul-Muqim [25] was 2.06 days which is shorter than the conclusion of this research work.

Conclusion

Proper evaluation of the patients before surgery, technically skilled professionals, and early mobilization & in time administration of the complications after surgery can decrease the prolonged stay in the hospital after surgery.

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